

Changes in phospholipid and lipid peroxidation levels due to latex of *Croton tiglium* in freshwater snail *Lymnaea acuminata*

Cambios en los niveles de peroxidación de fosfolípidos y lípidos por efecto del latex de *Croton tiglium* sobre el molusco dulceacuícola *Lymnaea acuminata*

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ABSTRACT

Exposure to 40% and 60% of LC₅₀ of 48h of the latex extract of *Croton tiglium* Linn (Euphorbiaceae) for 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h significantly reduced the endogenous levels of phospholipid and increased the rate of lipid peroxidation in brain and foot tissue of *Lymnaea (Radix) acuminata* Lamarck. Alteration in the levels of phospholipid and rate of lipid peroxidation were time and dose dependent. It is concluded that latex extract of *Croton tiglium* or its metabolites increase peroxidation of lipids in *Lymnaea acuminata*, which brings about change in membrane permeability to various ions and may thus be the cause of the toxicity of this plant extract.

RESUMEN

La exposición a LC₅₀ de 48 horas del extracto del latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40% y 60% durante 24, 48, 72 y 96 horas redujo significativamente los niveles de fosfolípidos e incrementó la tasa de peroxidación de lípidos en los tejidos cerebral y del pie de *Lymnaea (Radix) acuminata* Lamarck. Ambos cambios dependen tanto del tiempo como de la dosis. Esto confirma que dicho latex o sus metabolitos incrementa la peroxidación de lípidos en el molusco, por medio de cambios en la permeabilidad de la membrana a varios iones. Esta puede ser la causa de la toxicidad del extracto de esta planta.

KEY WORDS: Lipid peroxidation, phospholipids level, latex of *Croton tiglium*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Peroxidación de lípidos, niveles de fosfolípidos, latex de *Croton tiglium*.

INTRODUCTION

The snail *Lymnaea acuminata* is the vector of liver flukes *Fasciola hepatica* and *Fasciola gigantica*, which cause endemic fascialiasis in cattle and liver stock in northern parts of India (YADAV,

SINGH AND SINGH, 2002; TRIPATHI AND SINGH, 2003; SINGH AND SINGH, 2003). Heavy use of synthetic pesticides/ synthetic pyrethroids for the control of aquatic vectors created other serious

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problems to the aquatic environment (SASTRY AND SHUKLA, 1993; DEVI, 1997). Their hazardous nature has prompted scientists to find out non-disruptive, suitable and newer options for the control of weed and aquatic pests. In recent times, the use of natural pesticides has gained popularity all over the world. These plant products are the focus of attention as a suitable alternative to synthetic pesticides due to some ideal properties i.e. low cost, easy availability and biodegradability in nature (MARSTON AND HOSTETTMAN, 1985; SINGH AND SINGH, 2002).

A large number of plant pesticides are lethal to aquatic snails (GODAN, 1983; SINGH, SINGH, MISRA AND AGARWAL, 1996). SINGH AND AGARWAL, (1984 a, b) for the first time reported that the lattices of euphorbiales are highly toxic to snails. Later SINGH AND AGARWAL (1992; 1993 and 1995) reported several euphorbious species (falta algo :p.ej.species) as plant molluscicides. It is known that the primary target of these plant molluscicides is the nervous system (SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1984a, b). It was observed that these plant molluscicides affect acetylcholine, dopamine and non-epinephrine levels in nervous tissues of exposed animals (SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1995). Evidences for tissues injury induced by certain anti cholinesterase (Anti-AChE) pesticides has been shown to be associated with increased fragility of various biological membranes and the structural lipids of biomembranes undergo peroxidation decomposition (CHVAPIL, RYAN AND BRADA, 1972).

YADAV AND SINGH (2001, 2002) reported that latex extract of *Codiaeum variegatum* and *Croton tiglium* have high molluscicidal and anti-cholinesterase activity against snails *Lymnaea acuminata* and *Indoplanorbis exustus*. In the present work the author is interested in knowing the sub-lethal effects of the latex extract of *Croton tiglium* on the endogenous level of phospholipids and rate of lipid peroxidation level in nervous and foot tissues of the freshwater snail *Lymnaea acuminata* to see if it can serve as effective molluscicides.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Adult *Lymnaea acuminata* (2.4 ± 0.4 cm in length) were collected from local ponds and acclimatized in the laboratory for 96h in dechlorinated tap water. Batches of 50 snails were kept in 12L glass aquaria containing 6L-dechlorinated tap water. Snails were treated according to methods of SINGH AND AGARWAL (1986). Experiments were carried out at 24-26 °C. No food was given during the course of the experiment. There was no mortality in either controls or experiments. Oxygen concentration was normal in control animals as there was no sign of oxygen deficiency stress. 40 snails / 5L water were used which caused no oxygen stress in test snails. The snails were exposed to 40% (0.016 mg/L) and 60% (0.024 mg/L) of 48h LC₅₀ of 0.04 mg/L for 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h. These doses were based on 48h LC₅₀ values reported by YADAV AND SINGH, (2001). After 24h, 48h, 72h or 96h the snails were removed from the aquaria and rinsed in water. Control groups were kept in de-chlorinated tap water without any treatment. Endogenous levels of phospholipids were determined in nervous and foot tissue by the method of FISKE AND ROW, (1925) as modified by DITTMER AND MICHAEL (1965), and modified for snails by SINGH, SINGH AND AGARWAL (1993). The rate of lipid peroxidation was determined in nervous and foot tissues by the methods of (UTELY, BERMHEIM AND HOCHTEIN, 1967).

Phospholipids levels estimation: Brain and foot tissue were dissected out and placed on filter paper for removal of adherent water. 300 mg each of brain and foot tissues were used for each replicate. Brain tissue was pooled from eighty five snails. The tissues were then homogenized in chloroform/methanol mixture (2:1v/v) using a Teflon pestle to give a 5% w/v homogenate. Supernatants were filtered and two drops of 0.05M NaCl solutions was added to the supernatant and left for 24h. After 24h the upper layer was discarded. 1 mL of lipid layer was placed in a test tube and solvent was removed by heating in a boiling water bath. 1 mL of distilled water and 0.4 mL of 10% trichloroacetic acid was added to this and

Table I. *In vivo* effect of exposure to 40% and 60% of 48h LC₅₀ of latex of *Croton tiglium* on the levels of phospholipids in the nervous and foot tissues of snail *L. acuminata* after exposure to 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h. Values are mean \pm SE of six replicates. Values in parenthesis indicate % of control. Student test "t" test demonstrated that the treated values were significantly different from control ($P < 0.05$). Two-way analysis of variance demonstrated that the changes were dose and time dependent. 300 mg nervous and foot tissues were taken for all estimations.

Table I. Efecto in vivo de la exposición al 40% y 60% de 48h LC₅₀ del latex de *Croton tiglium* en los niveles de fosfolípidos en los tejidos nervioso y del pie de *L. acuminata* tras 24h, 48h, 72h y 96h de exposición. Los valores son la media \pm SE de 6 réplicas. Valores en paréntesis indican % del control. El test "t" de Student muestra que los valores tratados son significativamente diferentes de los del control ($P < 0.05$). El análisis de varianza de dos vías demuestra que los cambios dependen de la dosis y el tiempo. Se usaron 300 mg de tejido nervioso y del pie en todas las estimaciones.

	Tissues	40% of LC ₅₀ (48h)	60% of LC ₅₀ (48h)
Control	Brain	23.26 \pm 0.15 (100)	23.26 \pm 0.15 (100)
	Foot	21.01 \pm 0.31 (100)	21.01 \pm 0.31 (100)
24h	Brain	17.45 \pm 0.18 (62.12)	13.26 \pm 0.22 (57.00)
	Foot	18.00 \pm 0.18 (85.67)	16.3 \pm 0.17 (77.58)
48h	Brain	14.19 \pm 0.39 (60.99)	13.5 \pm 0.7 (51.52)
	Foot	14.95 \pm 0.26 (71.15)	13.22 \pm 0.19 (62.92)
72h	Brain	13.02 \pm 0.19 (55.96)	11.00 \pm 0.25 (47.29)
	Foot	11.29 \pm 0.33 (53.73)	10.64 \pm 0.39 (50.64)
96h	Brain	9.2 \pm 0.23 (39.55)	8.67 \pm 0.20 (37.27)
	Foot	9.63 \pm 0.34 (45.83)	8.23 \pm 0.28 (39.317)

heated. After this, 0.4 mL of 2.5 % Ammonium molybdate solutions and 0.2 mL of amino naphthosulphonic acid was added and the mixture heated at 80°C for 15 min, cooled and diluted with 4 ml distilled water. After 5 minutes the absorbance was read at 640 nm with the help of a spectrophotometer (No. 106 S.No. 3265 Systronics). The blank consisted of 1 mL distilled water, 0.4 mL 10% dichloroacetic acid, 0.4 mL 2.5% ammonium molybdate solution, 0.2 mL of aminonaphthosulphonic acid and 4.0 mL distilled water but no tissue homogenate. Standards curves were prepared by reading the absorbance of different concentrations of monopotassium phosphate solutions containing 0.008 to 0.04 mg of pure salt.

Lipid peroxidation estimation: Brain and foot tissues (100 mg each) were homogenized in chilled 0.15 M KCl solution using a Teflon pestle to give a 10% w/v homogenate. 1 ml aliquots of the homogenate were incubated at 37°C for 2h, following which 1.0 ml of 10% (w/v)

trichoroacetic acid was added. After thorough mixing, the mixture was centrifuged at 2200g for 10 min and 1ml of supernatant was then taken with an equal volume of 0.67% (w/v) 2-thiobarbituric acid (Sigma Chemical Company, USA) and kept in a boiling water bath for 10 min, cooled and diluted with one ml of distilled water. The absorbance read at 535 nm against a blank containing only KCl solution and results were expressed as μ mol of malonaldehyde formed per 30 min/mg tissue. The extinction coefficient was 1.56 \times 10⁵ as described by UTELY ET AL., (1967). The methods of SOKAL AND ROHLF (1973) were applied for analysis of students "t" test and two-way analysis of variance ($P < 0.05$).

RESULTS

The endogenous levels of phospholipids in the brain and foot tissues were 23.26 and 21.01 mg/g, respectively. *In vivo* 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h exposure to

Table II. *In vivo* effect of exposure to 40% and 60% of 48h LC₅₀ of *Croton tiglium* on the rate of lipid peroxidation in the nervous and foot tissues of snail *L. acuminata* after exposure to 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h. Values are mean \pm SE of six replicates. Values in parenthesis indicate % of control. Student test "t" test demonstrated that the treated values were significantly different from control ($P < 0.05$). Two-way analysis of variance demonstrated that the changes were dose and time dependent. 600 mg nervous and foot tissues were taken for all estimations.

Table II. Efecto in vivo de la exposición al 40% y 60% de 48h LC₅₀ del latex de *Croton tiglium* en los niveles de fosfolípidos en los tejidos nervioso y del pie de *L. acuminata* tras 24h, 48h, 72h y 96h de exposición. Los valores son la media \pm SE de 6 réplicas. Valores en paréntesis indican % del control. El test "t" de Student muestra que los valores tratados son significativamente diferentes de los del control ($P < 0.05$). El análisis de varianza de dos vías demuestra que los cambios dependen de la dosis y el tiempo. Se usaron 600 mg de tejido nervioso y del pie en todas las estimaciones.

	Tissues	40% of LC ₅₀ (48h)	60% of LC ₅₀ (48h)
Control	Brain	2.49 \pm 0.24 (100)	2.49 \pm 0.24 (100)
	Foot	1.61 \pm 0.06 (100)	1.61 \pm 0.06 (100)
24h	Brain	3.00 \pm 0.07 (120.48)	3.33 \pm 0.13 (133.73)
	Foot	1.89 \pm 0.02 (117.39)	2.41 \pm 0.04 (149.68)
48h	Brain	3.28 \pm 0.065 (131.72)	3.61 \pm 0.053 (144.97)
	Foot	2.01 \pm 0.06 (124.84)	2.64 \pm 0.05 (163.97)
72h	Brain	3.64 \pm 0.060 (146.18)	4.19 \pm 0.058 (168.27)
	Foot	3.16 \pm 0.039 (196.27)	3.75 \pm 0.11 (232.91)
96h	Brain	5.18 \pm 0.04 (208.03)	6.42 \pm 0.07 (257.83)
	Foot	4.73 \pm 0.17 (293.78)	6.40 \pm 0.30 (397.51)

40% and 60% LC₅₀ (48h) of *C. tiglium* caused a significant change in levels of phospholipids (Table I) and activity of lipid peroxidation (Table II) in the nervous and foot tissues of the snails. Treatment with 40% LC₅₀ of latex extract of *C. tiglium* for 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h decreased the levels of phospholipids in the brain tissues up to 62.1, 60.99, 55.96 and 39.55 % of the control, respectively (Table I). Likewise in foot tissue, it decreased to 85.67, 71.15, 53.73, and 45.83 % of the control respectively (Table I). With exposure to a higher dose i.e. 60% of 48h LC₅₀ for 24h, 48h, 72h and 96h, there was a further decrease in the endogenous levels of phospholipids (Table II).

The rate of lipid peroxidation in the brain and foot tissues of control snails was 2.53 and 1.66 mol malonaldehyde formed/ 30min/ mg, respectively. Exposure to the two doses of latices of *C. tiglium* increased the rate of lipid peroxidation in both the nervous and foot tissues. Exposure to 40% of LC₅₀ for 24h,

48h, 72h and 96h increased this to 120.48, 131.72, 146.18 and 208.03 % of control in brain tissue and to 117.39, 124.84, 196.27 and 293.78 % of control in foot tissue, respectively. Exposure to 60% of LC₅₀ (48h) caused a greater increase in the rate of lipid peroxidation (Table II). Analysis of variance demonstrated that the increase in the rate of lipid peroxidation was time as well as dose dependent ($P < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

The data obtained indicate that exposure of *Lymnaea acuminata* to latex of *C. tiglium*, increased the rate of lipid peroxidation along with decrease in the endogenous levels of phospholipids in the nervous and foot tissue of the snail. That these effects were indeed caused by latices of *C. tiglium* is evidenced by the fact that both changes were time as well as dose dependent.

Biological membranes are known to be rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids. In fact, lipids may account for 28% to 79% of the mass of cell membranes. While the inner mitochondrial membrane contains about 60% proteins and only 20% lipids, the myelin sheath of the brain contains as much as 80% lipids and only 20% protein. Most snail membranes, however, contain nearly equal amounts of protein and fat. Membrane lipids are mainly phospholipids and most of them are polyglycerides. Up to 20% of the phospholipids are acidic which are negatively charged and are associated with membrane proteins due to lipid protein interaction (LEHNINGER, 1987).

Several workers reported that synthetic / plant pesticides cause repetitive discharges due to prolongation of sodium current and increased depolarization (NARAHASHI, 1983; UPRETI ET AL, 1991; SIDDIQUI, SAYEED, ZAFAR AND ISLAM, 2002). The site of action is most likely to be within the lipophilic environment of the membrane in the neighbourhood of sodium proteins (OSBORNE AND SMALL-COMBE, 1983; PATEL, FULLONE AND ANDERS, 1992). Any change in the structure of the concentration of lipids would radically alter the structure of membranes, bringing about a change in their permeability characteristic. Indeed, lipid peroxidation has been reported to play an important role in a wide variety of pathological and degradative conditions (BUS AND GIBSON, 1979).

During lipid peroxidation, oxygen reacts with polyunsaturated lipids to form lipid radicals and semistable hydroperoxides. During this process hydrogen is abstracted from a carbon-carbon bond of unsaturated lipid. This process requires an initiator radical, which may

come from the metabolic degradation of an external agent (TAPPEL, 1973; ZIA AND ISLAM, 2000). According to BUS AND GIBSON (1983) certain classes of xenobiotics such as parquets and inorganic substances such as carbon tetrachloride lose a single electron but under aerobic conditions get re-oxidized immediately to their original compound with the concurrent formation of a super-oxide radical. Toxicity of these compounds is due to their ability to initiate the generation or induction of this superoxide anion radical. A similar mechanism may be possible in the case of *L. acuminata* treated with latexes of *C. tiglium*. Formation of activated oxygen can have extremely detrimental consequences not only for phospholipids but also for proteins, nucleic acids and polysaccharides (BUS AND GIBSON, 1983; SINGH ET AL., 1996). Even through the mechanism of formation of superoxide in the case of *C. tiglium* is not known yet, it is possible that the metabolic degradation of this extract produces an initiator organic radical which is capable of starting the peroxidation reaction. It is clear that the latex extract of *Croton tiglium* is highly effective at a lower dose and may eventually prove to be a very useful molluscicide.. Their effectiveness/ attractiveness as molluscicides in comparison to synthetic pesticides lie in their plant origin, which makes them inexpensive and more easily biodegradable and safe for non-target organisms.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BUS, J. S. AND GIBSON, J. E., 1979. Lipid peroxidation and its role in toxicity. In: Hodgson, E., Bend, J. R. and Philpot, R. M. (eds) *Review in biochemical Toxicology* 1: 125-149.
- BUS, J. S. AND GIBSON, J. E., 1983. Oxygen activation and lipoperoxidative metabolism of toxicity of pesticides and other xenobiotics. In: Miyamoto, J. and Kerney, P. C. (eds) *Pesticides Chemistry*. Human welfare and Environment. Pergmon Press, London & New York, 3 Pp-457 - 62.

- CHVAPIL, M., RYAN, J. N. AND BRADA, Z., 1972. Effect of selected chelating agents and metals on stability of liver lysosome. *Biochemistry and Pharmacology* 21:1097-1105.
- DEVI, U., 1997. Heavy metal toxicity to gastropod, *Morula granulata*: tolerance to copper, mercury, zinc and cadmium. *Journal of Environmental Biology* 18 (3): 287-290.
- DITTMER, J. C. AND MICHAEL, A. W., 1965. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of lipids and lipid components. In: methods of Enzymology. Colowick, S. P. and Kaplan, N. O. (eds). Vol XIV. Academic Press. Pp - 483.
- FISKE, C. H. AND ROW, Y., 1925. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of lipids and lipid components. In: methods of Enzymology. Colowick, S. P. and Kaplan, N. O. (eds). Vol. XIV. Academic Press. Pp 483.
- GODAN, D., 1983. Pest sludge and snail, Biology and control (ed., Dora Godan) translated by Sheila Gruber, Springer verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York.
- LEHNINGER, A. L., 1987. Principles of Biochemistry. 2nd Indian reprints. CBC Publisher and Distributors Delhi Pp - 1011
- MARSTON, A. AND HOSTETTSMANN, K., 1985. Plant molluscicide. *Phytochemistry* 24: 639-652.
- NARAHASHI, T., 1985. Nerve membrane ionic channels as the primary target of pyrethroids. *Neuro toxicology* 6: 3-22.
- OSBORNE, P. AND SMALLCOMBE, A., 1983. Site of actions of pyrethroid insecticides In: Miyamoto, J. and Kerney, P. C. (eds). Human welfare and Environment. Pergmon Press, London and New York *Pesticides Chemistry* 3: 372.
- PATEL, N., FULLONE, J. AND ANDERS, M. W., 1992. Brain uptake and metabolism of S-(1,2-dichlorovinyl) glutathione (DCVG) and S-(1,2-Dichlorovinyl)-L cystine (DCVC). *Toxicology* 12: 343-346.
- SASTRY, K. V. AND SHUKLA, V., 1993. Uptake and distribution of cadmium in tissue of *Channa marulius*. *Journal of Environmental Biology* 14 (2): 137 - 142.
- SIDDIQI, A., SAYEED, I., ZAFAR, K. S. AND ISLAM, F., 2002. Argemone oil augmented oxidative stress in discrete areas of rat brain. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* 69: 734 - 740.
- SINGH, A. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1992. Molluscicidal activity of euphorbiales against the snail *Indoplanorbis exustus*. *Acta Hydrochimica et Hydrobiologica* 20: 262- 264.
- SINGH, A., SINGH, D. K. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1993. Effect of cypermethrin, mexacarbate and phorate on phospholipid and lipideroxidation in the snail *Lymnaea acuminata*. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* 51: 68-71.
- SINGH, A. SINGH, D. K., MISRA, T. N. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1996. Molluscicides of plant origin. *Biological Agriculture and Horticulture* 13: 205-252.
- SINGH, D. AND SINGH, A., 2002. Piscicidal effects of some common plants of India used in freshwater bodies against target animals. *Chemosphere* 49 (1): 45-49.
- SINGH, D. K. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1986. Piperonyl butoxide synergism with two synthetic pyrethroids against *Lymnaea acuminata*. *Chemosphere* 15: 493-498.
- SINGH, D. K. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1984a. Alteration of biogenic level in the snail *Lymnaea acuminata* by the latex of *Euphorbia royleana*. *Toxicological Letters* 21: 309-314.
- SINGH, D. K. AND AGARWAL R. A., 1984b. Correlation of the anti-cholinesterase and molluscicidal activity of the latex of *Euphorbia royleana* Bioss. on *Lymnaea acuminata*. *Journal of Natural Product* 47: 702-705.
- SINGH, A. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1990. Molluscicidal and Anti-Cholinesterase activity of euphorbiales. *Biological Agriculture and Horticulture* 7: 81-91.
- SINGH, D. K., SINGH, A. AND AGARWAL, R. A., 1993. *Nerium indicum* as a potent molluscicide of plant origin. *Journal of Medical and Applied Malacology* 5: 93-95.
- SINGH, K. AND SINGH, D. K., 1995. Effect of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) on biochemical parameters in ovotestis of *Lymnaea acuminata*. *Malaysian Applied Biology* 24: 7-11.
- SINGH, S. K. AND SINGH, A., 2003. Effect of the plants *Thevetia peruviana* and *Alstonia scholaris* (Family: Apocynaceae) on acetylcholinesterase activity of *Lymnaea acuminata* snails. *Egyptian Journal of Schistosomiasis Infectious & Endemic Disease* 25:
- SOKAL, R. R. AND ROHLF, F. J., 1973. Introduction to bio-statistic edited by Freeman, M. N., San Francisco. Pp. 368.
- TAPPEL, A. L., 1973. Lipid peroxidation damage to cell component. *Federation Proceedings* 32: 1870-1874.
- TRIPATHI, P. K. AND SINGH, A., 2003. Toxic effects of dimethoate and carbaryl pesticides on protein metabolism of freshwater snail *Lymnaea acuminata*. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination Toxicology* 70: 146-152.
- UPRETI, K. K., DAS, M. AND KHANNA, S. K., 1991. Biochemical toxicology of Argemone oil: effect on hepatic cyt P-450 and Xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes. *Journal of Applied Toxicology* 11: 203-209.
- UTELY, H. C., BERMHEIM, F. AND HOCHTEIN, P., 1967. Effects of sulfhydryl reagent on peroxidation in microsome. *Achieves of Biochemistry and Biophysics* 188: 29-32.
- YADAV, R. P. AND SINGH, A., 2001. Environmentally safe molluscicide from two common Euphorbiales. *Iberus* 19 (1): 65-73.

- YADAV, R. P. AND SINGH, A., 2002. Toxic effect of *Croton tiglium* on *L. acuminata* and non-target fish *Channa punctatus*. *Iberus* 20 (2): 31-44.
- YADAV, R. P., SINGH, S. K. AND SINGH, A., 2002. Molluscicidal activity of *Codiaeum variegatum*, effects on snail metabolism. *Journal of Ecophysiology and Occupational Health* 2: 73 - 84.
- ZIA, S. AND ISLAM, F., 2000. Selenium altered the levels of lipids, lipid peroxidation and sulphydryl group in straitum and thalamus of rat *Biology of Trace Element Research* 77: 251-259.

